

MAX PLANCK INSTITUTE
FOR DYNAMICS OF COMPLEX
TECHNICAL SYSTEMS
MAGDEBURG

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS IN
SYSTEMS AND CONTROL THEORY

A Low-Rank Parareal Solver for Differential Riccati Equations Written in Julia

Jonas Schulze

May 10, 2022

Faculty of Mathematics
Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg

1. Motivation

2. Mathematical Details

Low-Rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorization

Rosenbrock Method

Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Parareal Method

3. Implementation

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

Parareal.jl

Parareal Runtime Estimation

4. Results

Numerical Results

Parallel Scaling

Conclusion

1. Motivation

2. Mathematical Details

Low-Rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorization

Rosenbrock Method

Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Parareal Method

3. Implementation

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

Parareal.jl

Parareal Runtime Estimation

4. Results

Numerical Results

Parallel Scaling

Conclusion

Optimal Control Problem

Consider the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) problem

$$\min_u \int_{t_0}^{t_f} y^T y + u^T u dt + \frac{1}{100} y(t_f)^T y(t_f)$$

$$\text{s.t. } E\dot{x} = Ax + Bu$$

$$y = Cx$$

using

- state $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$
- control $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $m \ll n$
- output $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, $q \ll n$
- constant system matrices E, A, B, C .

Feedback Law (e.g. Locatelli 2001)

The optimal control is given by

$$u(t) = -B^T X(t_f + t_0 - t) E x(t)$$

where $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ solves the differential Riccati equation (DRE)

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{X} E = C^T C + A^T X E + E^T X A \\ \quad \quad \quad - E^T X B B^T X E \\ E^T X(t_0) E = \frac{1}{100} C^T C. \end{cases}$$

Optimal Control Problem

Consider the linear quadratic regulator (LQR) problem

$$\min_u \int_{t_0}^{t_f} y^T y + u^T u dt + \frac{1}{100} y(t_f)^T y(t_f)$$

$$\text{s.t. } E\dot{x} = Ax + Bu$$

$$y = Cx$$

using

- state $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$
- control $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, $m \ll n$
- output $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$, $q \ll n$
- constant system matrices E, A, B, C .

Feedback Law (e.g. Locatelli 2001)

The optimal control is given by

$$u(t) = -B^T X(t_f + t_0 - t) E x(t)$$

where $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ solves the differential Riccati equation (DRE)

$$\begin{cases} E^T \dot{X} E = C^T C + A^T X E + E^T X A \\ \quad \quad \quad - E^T X B B^T X E \\ E^T X(t_0) E = \frac{1}{100} C^T C. \end{cases}$$

- Benner and Saak 2005
- Linearized 2D heat equation:

$$\begin{aligned} c\rho\partial_t x &= \lambda \Delta x, & x \in \Omega \\ \lambda\partial_n x &= q_k(u_k - x), & x \in \Gamma_k, k = 1, \dots, 7 \\ \partial_n x &= 0, & x \in \Gamma_0 \end{aligned}$$

- FEM discretizations / mesh refinements with $n \in \{371, 1357, 5177, 20\,209, \dots\}$ states, $m = 7$ inputs, $q = 6$ outputs
- Time horizon $t \in [0\text{ s}, 45\text{ s}]$
- Resulting (E, A, B, C) system: $E \succ 0$ and $A \prec 0$
 \rightsquigarrow uniquely solvable

- Large-scale problems: a single (dense) $X(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ takes 200 TB for $n = 5\,000\,000$
 - Solution X is symmetric and dense, but has low rank (e.g. Penzl 2000)
- ↪ Approximation via low-rank symmetric indefinite factorization:

$$X \approx L D L^T$$

- DRE is highly stiff, i.e. high accuracy requires small time steps or high orders
- ↪ Parareal method for speed-up

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

1. Motivation

2. Mathematical Details

Low-Rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorization

Rosenbrock Method

Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Parareal Method

3. Implementation

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

Parareal.jl

Parareal Runtime Estimation

4. Results

Numerical Results

Parallel Scaling

Conclusion

- Benner, Li, and Truhar 2009
- Arithmetic:

$$\begin{bmatrix} | & \\ \hline \text{---} & \\ \hline | & \end{bmatrix} \pm \begin{bmatrix} | & \\ \hline \text{---} & \\ \hline | & \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} | & | \\ \hline & \\ \hline | & | \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{---} & \\ \hline \pm & \text{---} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{---} \\ \hline \text{---} \\ \hline \end{bmatrix}$$

- Problem: growing storage requirements, e.g.

$$\begin{bmatrix} | & \\ \hline \text{---} & \\ \hline | & \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} | & \\ \hline \text{---} & \\ \hline | & \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} | & | & | \\ \hline & & \\ \hline | & | & | \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{---} & \\ \hline & \text{---} \\ \hline & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{---} \\ \hline \text{---} \\ \hline \end{bmatrix}$$

↪ Lang 2017: column compression technique

- “Low-rank” versions of a matrix or algorithm refer to LRSIF

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

For the initial value problem (IVP) $\dot{x} = f(x)$ on a time grid $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N = t_f$, the method reads

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_{n+1} := x_n + \tau \sum_{j=1}^s b_j k_j \\ k_i := f \left(x_n + \tau \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \alpha_{ij} k_j \right) + \tau \mathcal{J} \sum_{j=1}^i \gamma_{ij} k_j \\ \text{for } i = 1, \dots, s, \end{array} \right.$$

where $\mathcal{J} := f'(x_n)$ denotes the Jacobian.

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

1st Order Scheme (Linearly Implicit Euler Scheme)

For the IVP $\dot{x} = f(x)$ the method reads

$$\begin{cases} x_{n+1} = x_n + \tau k_1 \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_1 = f(x_n). \end{cases}$$

2nd Order Scheme (Verwer et al. 1999)

$$\begin{cases} x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{3}{2}\tau k_1 + \frac{1}{2}\tau k_2 \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_1 = f(x_n) \\ (I - \gamma\tau \mathcal{J})k_2 = f(x_n + \tau k_1) - 2k_1 \end{cases}$$

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Consider the DRE $E^T \dot{X} E = \mathcal{R}(X)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(X_n) &= C^T C + A^T X_n E + E^T X_n A - E^T X_n B B^T X_n E \\ \mathcal{J}(U) &= 0 + A^T U E + E^T U A - E^T U B B^T X_n E \\ &\quad - E^T X_n B B^T U E \\ &= (A - B B^T X_n E)^T U E + E^T U (A - B B^T X_n E) \end{aligned}$$

- The Jacobian is a Lyapunov operator!
- ↪ $I - \gamma \tau \mathcal{J}$ is a Lyapunov operator, i.e. all Rosenbrock stages are Algebraic Lyapunov Equations (ALEs).

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Consider the DRE $E^T \dot{X} E = \mathcal{R}(X)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(X_n) &= C^T C + A^T X_n E + E^T X_n A - E^T X_n B B^T X_n E \\ \mathcal{J}(U) &= 0 + A^T U E + E^T U A - E^T U B B^T X_n E \\ &\quad - E^T X_n B B^T U E \\ &= (A - B B^T X_n E)^T U E + E^T U (A - B B^T X_n E) \end{aligned}$$

- The Jacobian is a Lyapunov operator!
- ↪ $I - \gamma \tau \mathcal{J}$ is a Lyapunov operator, i.e. all Rosenbrock stages are Algebraic Lyapunov Equations (ALEs).

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Consider the DRE $E^T \dot{X} E = \mathcal{R}(X)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(X_n) &= C^T C + A^T X_n E + E^T X_n A - E^T X_n B B^T X_n E \\ \mathcal{J}(U) &= 0 + A^T U E + E^T U A - E^T U B B^T X_n E \\ &\quad - E^T X_n B B^T U E \\ &= (A - B B^T X_n E)^T U E + E^T U (A - B B^T X_n E) \end{aligned}$$

- The Jacobian is a Lyapunov operator!

↪ $I - \gamma \tau \mathcal{J}$ is a Lyapunov operator, i.e. all Rosenbrock stages are Algebraic Lyapunov Equations (ALEs).

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Consider the DRE $E^T \dot{X}E = \mathcal{R}(X)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(X_n) &= C^T C + A^T X_n E + E^T X_n A - E^T X_n B B^T X_n E \\ \mathcal{J}(U) &= 0 + A^T U E + E^T U A - E^T U B B^T X_n E \\ &\quad - E^T X_n B B^T U E \\ &= (A - B B^T X_n E)^T U E + E^T U (A - B B^T X_n E) \end{aligned}$$

- The Jacobian is a Lyapunov operator!
- ↪ $I - \gamma \tau \mathcal{J}$ is a Lyapunov operator, i.e. all Rosenbrock stages are Algebraic Lyapunov Equations (ALEs).

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Linearly implicit Euler scheme
- Mena 2007: Formulation for DRE $E^T \dot{X} E = \mathcal{R}(X)$
- Lang 2017: Formulation for LRSIF $X(t) = LDL^T$
- 1 ALE per step:

$$\tilde{A}_n^T X_{n+1} E + E^T X_{n+1} \tilde{A}_n = -GSG^T$$

where $X_n = LDL^T$ and

$$\tilde{A}_n = \gamma\tau(A - BB^T X_n E) - \frac{1}{2}E$$

$$G = [C^T \quad E^T L]$$

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} I & \\ & DL^T BB^T LD + \frac{1}{\tau} D \end{bmatrix}$$

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

- Verwer et al. 1999
- Mena 2007: Formulation for DRE $E^T \dot{X} E = \mathcal{R}(X)$
- Lang 2017: Formulation for LRSIF $X(t) = LDL^T$
- 2 ALEs per step:

$$\begin{cases} X_{n+1} = X_n + (2 - \frac{1}{2\gamma})\tau K_1 - \frac{1}{2}\tau K_{21} \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_1 E + E^T K_1 \hat{A}_n = -\mathcal{R}(X_n) \\ \hat{A}_n^T K_{21} E + E^T K_{21} \hat{A}_n = -(\tau^2 K_1 B B^T K_1 + (2 - \frac{1}{\gamma})K_1) \end{cases}$$

(LRSIF right-hand sides not shown)

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

General Formulation (Peaceman and Rachford 1955)

For $Ax = b$ with $A = H + V$ the method reads

$$\begin{cases} H_k^+ x^{k+\frac{1}{2}} = b - V_k^- x^k \\ V_k^+ x^{k+1} = b - H_k^- x^{k+\frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

where $H_k^+ := H + \alpha_k I_n$, $V_k^+ := V + \beta_k I_n$, $H_k^- := H - \beta_k I_n$, $V_k^- := V - \alpha_k I_n$, and $\alpha_k, \beta_k \in \mathbb{C}$.

- Lang 2017: LRSIF formulation for ALE

$$\mathcal{L}(X) := A^T X E + E^T X A = -G S G^T$$

- Kürschner 2016: self-generating parameters

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

General Formulation (Lions, Maday, and Turinici 2001)

For the IVP $\dot{u} = f(u)$ the method reads

$$\begin{cases} U_{n+1}^0 := G(U_n^0) \\ U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k) \end{cases}$$

where $U_0^0 := u(t_0)$. U_n^k converges to $u(t_n)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

- Köhler, Saak, and Lang 2016 (GAMM): LRSIF formulation

- Speed-up $\approx t_F/t_G$ for large N , where $0 \leq n \leq N$.

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

General Formulation (Lions, Maday, and Turinici 2001)

For the IVP $\dot{u} = f(u)$ the method reads

$$\begin{cases} U_{n+1}^0 := G(U_n^0) \\ U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k) \end{cases}$$

where $U_0^0 := u(t_0)$. U_n^k converges to $u(t_n)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

- Köhler, Saak, and Lang 2016 (GAMM): LRSIF formulation

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{red bar} \\ \text{black bar} \\ \text{blue bar} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{red square} & & \\ & \text{black square} & \\ & & \text{blue square} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \text{red bar} \\ \text{black bar} \\ \text{blue bar} \end{bmatrix}$$

- Speed-up $\approx t_F/t_G$ for large N , where $0 \leq n \leq N$.

Big Picture

- Differential Riccati Equation (DRE)
- Solution in LRSIF
- Rosenbrock method to solve DRE
- Rosenbrock stages are ALEs
- ADI method to solve ALE
- Parareal method for speed-up

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure 6.4: Parareal method applied to a linear ODE

$$U_{n+1}^{k+1} := G(U_n^{k+1}) + F(U_n^k) - G(U_n^k)$$

Figure: Timeline diagram for $n \leq N = 10$ and $k \leq K = 4$

1. Motivation

2. Mathematical Details

Low-Rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorization

Rosenbrock Method

Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Parareal Method

3. Implementation

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

Parareal.jl

Parareal Runtime Estimation

4. Results

Numerical Results

Parallel Scaling

Conclusion


```
1 using DifferentialRiccatiEquations
2 using DrWatson, UnPack, MAT
3 using SparseArrays
4
5 P = matread(datadir("Rail371.mat"))
6 @unpack E, A, B, C = P
7
8 # low-rank
9 L = E \ collect(C')
10 D = spdiags(fill(0.01, size(L, 2)))
11 X0 = LDLT(L, D)
12
13 # dense
14 X0 = Matrix(X0)
15
16 tspan = (4500.0, 0.0)
17 prob = GDREProblem(E, A, B, C, X0, tspan)
18 sol = solve(prob, Ros1(); dt=(tspan[2]-tspan[1])/100)
```


Implementation

User Interface of Parareal.jl

```
1 using Distributed
2 using DrWatson, UnPack, MAT
3
4 addprocs() # or similar
5
6 @everywhere begin
7     using DifferentialRiccatiEquations, ParaReal
8     using DifferentialRiccatiEquations: DRESolution
9     using LinearAlgebra, SparseArrays
10
11     ParaReal.initial_value(p::GDREProblem) = p.X0
12     ParaReal.value(sol::DRESolution) = last(sol.X)
13
14     function ParaReal remake_prob(p::GDREProblem, X0, tspan)
15         GDREProblem(p.E, p.A, p.B, p.C, X0, tspan)
16     end
17
18     #...
```



```
18     #...
19
20     function Base.:(-)(X::LDLT{TL,TD}) where {TL,TD}
21         Ls = X.Ls
22         Ds = map(-, X.Ds)
23         LDLT{TL,TD}(Ls, Ds)
24     end
25
26     function LinearAlgebra.norm(X::LDLT)
27         L, D = X
28         norm((L'L)*D) # Frobenius
29     end
30
31     csolve(prob) = solve(prob, Ros1(); dt=prob.tspan[2] - prob.tspan[1])
32     fsolve(prob) = solve(prob, Ros1(); dt=(prob.tspan[2] - prob.tspan[1])/100)
33 end
34
35     #...
```



```
35 #...
36
37 P = matread(datadir("Rail371.mat"))
38 @unpack E, A, B, C = P
39 L = E \ collect(C')
40 D = spdiags(fill(0.01, size(L, 2)))
41  $X_0 = LDL^T(L, D)$ 
42 tspan = (4500.0, 0.0)
43
44 prob = ParaReal.Problem(GDREProblem(E, A, B, C,  $X_0$ , tspan))
45 alg = ParaReal.Algorithm(csolve, fsolve)
46 sol = solve(prob, alg; rtol=1e-6, nconverged=2)
```


Implementation

Effect of JIT Compiler Warm-Up

- No warm-up: sequential compilation
- Warming-up G : parallel compilation
- Warming-up F, G : no further benefit

~ Always warm-up G and G only

Figure 7.1: Timeline charts

```
bash fig:impl:warmup.job
```


- No warm-up: sequential compilation
- Warming-up G : parallel compilation
- Warming-up F, G : no further benefit

~ Always warm-up G and G only

Figure 7.1: Timeline charts

```
bash fig:impl:warmup.job
```

Runtime Model

$$\hat{t}_{\text{par}} := t_{\text{warm-up}} + \underbrace{N \cdot (t_{\text{ramp-up}} + t_G)}_{\substack{\text{stages } 1 \leq n \leq N \\ \text{refinement } k = 0}} + \underbrace{K \cdot (t_F + t_G)}_{\substack{n=N \\ 1 \leq k \leq K}} + t_F$$

- under suitable assumptions
- t_G/t_F : runtime of coarse/fine solver
- $t_{\text{warm-up}}$: duration of warm-up
- $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$: delay between first coarse solves

Figure: Timeline of $N = 8$ stages computing $K = 7$ refinements

Runtime Model

$$\hat{t}_{\text{par}} := t_{\text{warm-up}} + \underbrace{N \cdot (t_{\text{ramp-up}} + t_G)}_{\substack{\text{stages } 1 \leq n \leq N \\ \text{refinement } k = 0}} + \underbrace{K \cdot (t_F + t_G)}_{\substack{n=N \\ 1 \leq k \leq K}} + t_F$$

Table 7.1: Runtime measurements for dense Rail371. (timings in seconds)

warm-up	N	K	$t_{\text{warm-up}}$	$t_{\text{ramp-up}}$	t_G	t_F	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{par}	$\left \frac{\hat{t}_{\text{par}} - t_{\text{par}}}{t_{\text{par}}} \right $
none	8	7	0.00	10.45	1.40	13.69	215.85	214.04	0.008
G	8	7	11.00	1.78	1.38	14.05	155.98	158.32	0.015
G and F	8	7	24.66	1.81	1.39	14.00	171.88	171.89	<0.001

- $t_{\text{warm-up}}$: maximum
- t_F, t_G : median

- $t_{\text{ramp-up}}$: mean delay between first coarse solves minus t_G

- actual runtime t_{par} : end of last fine solve

1. Motivation

2. Mathematical Details

Low-Rank Symmetric Indefinite Factorization

Rosenbrock Method

Alternating-Directions Implicit Method

Parareal Method

3. Implementation

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

Parareal.jl

Parareal Runtime Estimation

4. Results

Numerical Results

Parallel Scaling

Conclusion

- ### Parareal Setup
- 450 coarse steps (100 ms)
 - 100 fine steps per coarse step (1 ms)
 - Max. #iterations: 10
 - Convergence: relative change in X below $371u_{\text{mach}}$, twice in a row, max. 1 iteration behind prev. stage, and all previous stages converged

Figure 7.7: Trajectory $X_{1,77}$ and relative error in K for Rail371

Figure 7.8: Rank of $X = LDL^T$ for Rail371

Parareal Setup

- 450 coarse steps (100 ms)
- 100 fine steps per coarse step (1 ms)
- Max. #iterations: 10
- Convergence: relative change in X below $371u_{\text{mach}}$, twice in a row, max. 1 iteration behind prev. stage, and all previous stages converged

Parareal Setup

- 450 coarse steps (100 ms)
- 100 fine steps per coarse step (1 ms)
- Max. #iterations: 10
- Convergence: relative change in X below $371u_{\text{mach}}$, twice in a row, max. 1 iteration behind prev. stage, and all previous stages converged

Figure 7.9: Timeline chart of parareal method applied to Rail371

Table 7.3: Speed-up and parallel efficiency of parareal method applied to Rail371 using $N = 450$ cores. (timings in seconds)

Solver	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{seq}	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{t_{\text{par}}}$	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{N \cdot t_{\text{par}}}$
LRSIF 1/1	1243.84	4313.10	3.47	0.008
LRSIF 1/2	1659.48	14 054.91	8.47	0.019
LRSIF 2/2	4417.83	24 565.04	5.56	0.012
Dense 1/1	3627.30	75 037.71	20.69	0.046
Dense 1/2	3956.86	84 595.61	21.38	0.048
Dense 2/2	3602.36	89 274.94	24.78	0.055
Dense 4/4	3381.88	115 091.06	34.03	0.076
Rail1357	3001.41	22 684.37	7.56	0.017*

Addendum

- Actual runtime of (sequential) Dense 4: $t_{\text{seq}} < 86\,831$ s (Slurm job duration)
- LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357:
 - 2 BLAS threads per process
 - 2× round-robin scheduling onto $P = 225$ processes
 - * actual efficiency: $2\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}/2P \cdot t_{\text{par}} = 0.034$

Table 7.3: Speed-up and parallel efficiency of parareal method applied to Rail371 using $N = 450$ cores. (timings in seconds)

Solver	t_{par}	\hat{t}_{seq}	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{t_{\text{par}}}$	$\frac{\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}}{N \cdot t_{\text{par}}}$
LRSIF 1/1	1243.84	4313.10	3.47	0.008
LRSIF 1/2	1659.48	14 054.91	8.47	0.019
LRSIF 2/2	4417.83	24 565.04	5.56	0.012
Dense 1/1	3627.30	75 037.71	20.69	0.046
Dense 1/2	3956.86	84 595.61	21.38	0.048
Dense 2/2	3602.36	89 274.94	24.78	0.055
Dense 4/4	3381.88	115 091.06	34.03	0.076
Rail1357	3001.41	22 684.37	7.56	0.017*

Addendum

- Actual runtime of (sequential) Dense 4: $t_{\text{seq}} < 86\,831$ s (Slurm job duration)
- LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357:
 - 2 BLAS threads per process
 - $2\times$ round-robin scheduling onto $P = 225$ processes
 - * actual efficiency: $2\hat{t}_{\text{seq}}/2P \cdot t_{\text{par}} = 0.034$

Parareal Method

- Offers large speed-ups, but has low efficiency
- Present implementation has severe ramp-up delay
due to Julia's JIT compiler warm-up
- Low-rank codes allow/require much smaller (temporal) resolutions to reach similar speed-ups as dense codes
- Runtime of low-rank solvers varies from evaluation to evaluation
due to varying rank and stiffness \rightsquigarrow complicates load balancing

DRE Solvers

- Ros1 performs identically for dense and low-rank data
- Reproduced issues with low-rank Ros2 in Julia
Lang, Mena, and Saak 2015 had used MATLAB

ParaReal.jl

- Currently limited to processes as executors
- Lacks asynchronous communication
- How to eliminate the ramp-up delay?
i.e. compile more code ahead-of-time
- How to improve load balancing?
e.g. via round-robin scheduling or threaded oversubscription;
but how to handle threads & processes?

DifferentialRiccatiEquations.jl

- Needs to record more metrics
- LDL^T (and LowRankUpdate) types could be separated into their own packages

5. Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

6. Errata: Parareal Reference Solution

5. Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

6. Errata: Parareal Reference Solution

Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Sequential Runtime for Larger Rail Configurations

Table: Runtime (as reported by Slurm) of low-rank Ros1 applied to larger Rail Configurations. (timings in minutes)

Size	#Steps	#Threads				
		1	2	4	8	16
1357	100	11:16	7:30	7:18	6:47	7:54
5177	10	10:14	6:14	4:29	3:57	4:00
20209	10	44:42	25:55	17:12	14:17	14:59

Parareal Runtime

Educated guesses:

- $t_G \approx \frac{7:30 \text{ min}}{100} = 4.5 \text{ s}$
- $t_F \approx 100t_G \approx 450 \text{ s}$
- $t_{\text{ramp-up}} \approx 2 \text{ s}$
- $\hat{t}_{\text{par}} \approx 130 \text{ min}$

Actual measurements:

- $t_{\text{par}} \approx 50 \text{ min}$
- overheads $\approx 10 \text{ min}$

• Runtime Model

• Parallel Scaling

```
export MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_N=100 MY_0=1
for c in 1 2 4 8 16; do
  sbatch --time=1:00:00 -n1 -c${c} -J lr${MY_RAIL}-c${c} seq.job
done
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Sequential Runtime for Larger Rail Configurations

Table: Runtime (as reported by Slurm) of low-rank Ros1 applied to larger Rail Configurations. (timings in minutes)

Size	#Steps	#Threads				
		1	2	4	8	16
1357	100	11:16	7:30	7:18	6:47	7:54
5177	10	10:14	6:14	4:29	3:57	4:00
20209	10	44:42	25:55	17:12	14:17	14:59

```
export MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_N=100 MY_0=1
for c in 1 2 4 8 16; do
  sbatch --time=1:00:00 -n1 -c${c} -J lr${MY_RAIL}-c${c} seq.job
done
```

Parareal Runtime

Educated guesses:

- $t_G \approx \frac{7:30 \text{ min}}{100} = 4.5 \text{ s}$
- $t_F \approx 100t_G \approx 450 \text{ s}$
- $t_{\text{ramp-up}} \approx 2 \text{ s}$
- $\hat{t}_{\text{par}} \approx 130 \text{ min}$

Actual measurements:

- $t_{\text{par}} \approx 50 \text{ min}$
- overheads $\approx 10 \text{ min}$

▶ Runtime Model

▶ Parallel Scaling

Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357


```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100  
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357


```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100  
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357


```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100  
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357

■ Stage $n = 384$

- had converged after $k = 7$ iterations,
- but restarts to be only 1 iteration behind stage $n - 1$,
- while also leaving the “converged” state

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389 also restart but only stages ≤ 387 stop being "converged"

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100  
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage $n = 387$ reaches maximum iteration $k = K = 10$ and converges

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357

- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406 converge early (i.e. $k < K$)

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406
- Stage 407
- Stages $408 \leq n \leq 415$ compute U_n^8 and converge

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406
- Stage 407
- Stages 408, ..., 415
- Stage $n = 416$ computes U_n^9 and converges

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406
- Stage 407
- Stages 408, ..., 415
- Stage 416
- Stages 417, ..., 449 hit $k = K$

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

Parareal Timeline of LRSIF 1/1 applied to Rail1357

- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406
- Stage 407
- Stages 408, ..., 415
- Stage 416
- Stages 417, ..., 449
- Stage 450 had converged, restarts, and hits $k = K$

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


- Stage 384
- Stages 385, ..., 389
- Stage 387
- Stages 388, ..., 406
- Stage 407
- Stages 408, ..., 415
- Stage 416
- Stages 417, ..., 449
- Stage 450
- The final gap on stage 449 is due to synchronous data transfer.

```
export MY_ROUNDROBIN=2 MY_RAIL=1357 MY_KIND=lowrank MY_NF=100
sbatch --time=4:00:00 -n 225 -c2 -J lr11 par.job
```


5. Addendum: Larger Rail Configurations

6. Errata: Parareal Reference Solution

- Thesis Figure 7.7: parareal order 4/4 [▶ goto](#)

```
MY_KIND=dense MY_NF=100 MY_OF=4 MY_OC=4 sbatch -n450 -c1 -J de44 par.job
```

- Better: sequential order 4

```
MY_KIND=dense MY_N=45000 MY_0=4 sbatch -n1 -c1 -J de4 seq.job
```

- But: relative error negligible

$$\frac{\|K_{\text{par}}(t) - K_{\text{seq}}(t)\|_F}{\|K_{\text{seq}}(t)\|_F} < 5u_{\text{mach}}$$

